

Original article

NANOCOMPOSITES BASED ON ISOTACTIC POLYPROPYLENE

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abstract

Studies have been carried out to identify the conditions for the formation of nanocomposites based on isotactic polypropylene (PP), maleinated PP (PPM) and their mixtures with modified montmorillonite (MMT Cloisite 20A). The conditions for the formation of exfoliated and intercalated nanocomposites depending on the concentration of Cloisite 20A and the ratio of PP/PMMA compositions are revealed. An increase in the modulus of elasticity for exfoliated nanocomposites by more than 40% was found while maintaining the elongation during fracture.

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Introduction

Due to the chemical resistance, high deformability, and good recyclability of polypropylene, they are widely used in various fields of production [1-4]. At the same time, low thermal stability, average elastic modulus, flammability, limit the possibilities their use as structural materials [5-7]. Some of these disadvantages are easily eliminated with the introduction of dispersed inorganic fillers, such as kaolin, calcium carbonate, quartz sand, wollastonite, chopped glass and carbon fibers, etc. However, to enhance a number of elastic - strength characteristics, high levels of filling are required to the detriment of deformation properties.

The problem of maintaining plasticity and simultaneously enhancing the elastic characteristics of the polymer matrix has been successfully solved on various polymers using nanotechnology approaches according to the "top-down" scheme on the example of inorganic layered silicate montmorillonite (MMT), the structure of which consists of layers 1 nm thick separated by bulk cations in the interlayer space [8,9] (the distance

between the layers is 0.96 nm). This space can be expanded to several nanometers due to the exchange of cations (Na^+ , Li^+ , etc.) for the hydrocarbon chain of the ammonium salt [10,11].

Polar polymers containing functional groups, due to the presence of specific interactions, diffuse into the interlayer space (MP) of MT during the mixing of components in the polymer melt. In the extreme case, the process is completed by exfoliation of MM particles to individual layers in the form of irregularly shaped disks (the perimeter of which is 300-400 nm), or the system is an integrated structure, macromolecules remain in the MP MT.

Based on these considerations, nanocomposites are classified as exfoliated, intercalated, intercalated-flocculated. The formation of a particular nanocomposite is facilitated by shear fields created during the mixing of components in the polymer melt. For nonpolar polymers, such as polypropylene, preliminary functionalization is necessary. The creation of such nanostructures in polymers provides record values in terms of modulus of elasticity, thermal stability and fire resistance while maintaining the initial deformation characteristics. In There are a number of studies in the literature [10,12-16] conducted on the basis of polypropylene, which show the fundamental possibility of creating nanocomposites with sufficiently high hardness, thermal stability and fire resistance. Nevertheless, due to the fact that the stages of formation of nanocomposites directly depend on many factors (molecular characteristics of PP, type of MMT and nature of the modifier, temperature, mixing speed and time, the level of introduced functionalized PP, etc.) in our opinion for each new pair of PP/ MMT it is necessary to search for optimal conditions for the formation of nanocomposites.

Based on the above, the purpose of this study is to search for conditions for the formation of nanostructures in isotactic PP (produced by Uz-Kor Gaz joint venture) in the presence of layered silicate "Cloisite 20A" and their relationship with the elastic-strength characteristics of nanocomposites.

Research methodology

Polypropylene ((PP) J150 granules obtained with the participation of the Sigler-Nat catalyst in the gas chemical complex of the Uz-Kor Gaz joint venture, Republic of Karakalpakstan, with the following properties were used as the starting material: melt flow rate (PTR) 8-12 g/10 minutes; $p(\text{am})=0.85 \text{ g/cm}^3$; $p(\text{kr})=0.95 \text{ g/cm}^3$; $p(\text{average})=0.90 \text{ g/cm}^3$. To improve the compatibility of PP with MMT, PP modified with maleic anhydride (PPMA) was used, the content of maleic anhydride was 0.25%. To obtain nanocomposites, PP and Cloisite 20A were dried in a vacuum oven at 70°C for 3 hours until moisture was completely removed. Composites were obtained on a

Brabender plastigraph (Plasticorder Brabender OHG DUISBURG (Germany)) for 15 minutes, at 50 rpm and a temperature of 180 ± 5 ° C.

The identification of samples was carried out on the basis of diffractograms, which were taken on the XRD-6100 apparatus (Shimadzu, Japan), controlled by a computer. CuK α radiation (β -filter, Ni, 1.54178 tube current and voltage mode 8 mA, 14 kV) and a constant detector rotation speed of 4 degrees/min with a step of 0.02 degrees were used. ($\omega/2\theta$ -coupling), and the scanning angle varied from 2 to 30°. The distance between the layers $d[001]$ was determined by the Wolfe-Bregg law: $2d\sin\theta = n\lambda$.

Physico-mechanical research. The stretching diagrams of the samples were determined on a universal testing machine Instron 3366 (USA) in uniaxial stretching mode with a set deformation rate in accordance with the requirements of ASTM D638-99 "Standard Test Method for the strength properties of plastics".

At least five samples of the test material made in the form of two-sided blades with a thickness of 2 mm were used for analysis. The deformation rate of the samples was 50 mm/min.

Results

Let us first consider the structure formation on the compositions of PPMA compositions with Cloisite 20A 97/3, 95/5, 93/7 % weight. accordingly.

In general, the structure of such compositions is an inhomogeneous morphology, in addition to partially intercalated and exfoliated formations, primary aluminosilicate particles are present in the composition of the composite that have not undergone changes. X-ray diffractograms on the studied samples are shown in Fig. 1. As can be seen in the diffraction spectrum of modified montmorillonite Cloisite 20A, a reflex [001] is observed at $2\theta=3.60$, corresponding to the interplane distance $d[001]=2.3$ nm., whereas for the initial unmodified Na MMT the reflex is observed at $2\theta=70$ with $d[001]=1.26$ nm. The introduction of Cloisite 20A particles into the polar polymer matrix, due to the specific interactions of the maleic groups of PPMA with the hydrophilic surface of the aluminosilicate and the modifier (quaternary ammonium salt), contribute to the diffusion of PP macromolecules into the interlayer space, which ends with the further expansion of the latter, up to the exfoliation of particles to individual layers. This process is facilitated by shear fields in the mixing chamber of the components in melt PP. The expansion of the interlayer space in aluminosilicate particles is fixed by the displacement of the reflex towards small angles of 2θ , and for exfoliated structures this reflex is practically absent. The PPMA composition with 3% weight corresponds to this case. the content of aluminosilicate, i.e. a fully exfoliated nanocomposite is formed. An increase in the filler content in the range of 5-7% by

weight already leads to the formation of intercalated (displacement of the reflex to small angles of 2θ) and exfoliated (a significant decrease in the intensity of the reflex) structures. Increase The concentration inevitably leads to the aggregation of aluminosilicate particles, which limits the diffusion of macromolecules into this space. A similar pattern is observed for mixtures of initial isotactic polypropylene with functionalized PP (5-20% by weight) with the introduction of 3% by weight. Cloisite 20A. Introduction of maleinated PP in the range of 5-20% by weight. Promotes the formation of generally mixed nanostructures, at 5% by weight, mainly exfoliated nanocomposites. The discovered structures, of course, should affect the elastic-strength characteristics of the composition. How It can be seen from Table 1. The fully exfoliated structure of PPMA / Cloisite 20A gives an increase in modulus of elasticity by more than 40%, mixed nanostructures formed at concentrations of 5 and 7% by weight of the filler of 28% and 24% , respectively.

Fig. 1. X-ray diffraction of filled polypropylene nanocomposite containing Cloisite 20A: 1 - 3% by weight, 2 - 5% by weight, 3 - 7% by weight, 4 - Cloisite 20A.

For a PP/PPMA composition with a polar component content of 5% by weight. the gain in modulus of elasticity is 23% and as it increases to 20% by weight, the gain effect is leveled due to an increase in the volume fraction of the low-modulus PPMA (the elastic modulus of the initial PP and PPMA are 365 and 285 MPa, respectively).

Table 1.

Tensile strength characteristics of nanocomposites based on polypropylene and modified montmorillonite

Name	Composition	ε	σ	E
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№	of the sample	% weight	Elongation when destroyed [%]	Mechanical stress [MRa]	Model Jung [MRa]
I series					
1	ПП(J-150)	100	10,28±0,08	37,49±0,16	364,5±3,27
2	ПП/ППМА/Cloisite 20A	92/5/3	9,28±0,27	41,52±0,53	448,75±10,66
3	ПП/ППМА/Cloisite 20A	87/10/3	9,52±0,44	37,72±0,31	398,5±18,35
4	ПП/ППМА/Cloisite 20A	77/20/3	9,47±0,23	34,5±0,69	364,5±7,08
II series					
5	ППМА	100	9,13±0,15	26,0±0,25	285,25±4,52
6	ППМА/Cloisite 20A	97/3	5,72±0,18	22,81±0,64	399,25±5,34
7	ППМА/Cloisite 20A	95/5	7,45±0,75	26,34±1,35	366,75±26,25
8	ППМА/Cloisite 20A	93/7	7,56±0,3	27,55±0,6	361,25±16,48

The effects of increasing the modulus of elasticity are accompanied in the case of a composition with PPMA by a noticeable drop in elongation during destruction, whereas in nanocomposites PP remains at the level of the original polypropylene. As expected, an increase in interfacial adhesion is manifested on the σ - ε curves by an increase in the maximum stress required for deformation of the composite.

Thus, it can be stated that the formation of exfoliated and intercalated nanocomposites with the introduction of small concentrations of layered aluminosilicate contributes to an increase in the modulus of elasticity by more than 40% while maintaining deformability.

Conclusion

The studies carried out to identify the necessary conditions for the formation of nanostructures in isotactic and maleinated polypropylene systems with modified aluminosilicate Cloisite 20A allow us to formulate the following conclusions

1. The principal possibility of creating nanocomposites based on PPMA and PP in the presence of PPMA (5-20% by weight) with exfoliated (at low concentrations of Cloisite 20A) and mixed with intercalated (at concentrations of Cloisite 20A more than 5% by weight) structures is shown.

2. It was found that the formation of exfoliated and intercalated nanocomposites leads to an increase in the elastic modulus by more than 40%, while this effect in PPMA-based composites is accompanied by a noticeable drop in elongation during

destruction, whereas in PP nanocomposites it remains at the level of the original polypropylene.

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